

ADJOINT OPTIMISATION OF INTERNAL TURBINE COOLING CHANNEL USING NODE AND CAD-BASED AUTOMATIC PARAMETRISATION METHODS

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SUMMARY

Aerodynamic shape optimisation with gradient-based methods is rapidly gaining popularity in the aerospace and automotive industries. The most effective method to compute the required sensitivities is the adjoint method which allows to compute sensitivities of an arbitrary number of design variables at constant computational cost. This in turn opens up a wide range of possibilities to parametrise the shape as the number of design variables is no longer a limiting factor as long as the parametrisation algorithm can also have differentiated in reverse mode.

A wide range of parametrisations have been proposed for aerodynamic shape optimisation [1]. On the one hand we will consider a node-based parametrisation which uses the surface nodes of the CFD grid as design variables. On the other hand, we will consider CAD-based parametrisations based on open-source CAD-kernel OpenCascade Technology (OCCT). Adjoint methods do not penalise the size of the design space, hence we can consider very large spaces that guarantee to incorporate the largest possible number of degrees of freedom. In this work, we use in-house compressible discrete adjoint solver, STAMPS [2], derived from the flow solver using the automatic differentiation (AD) tool Tapenade.

1: Geometric Shape Parametrisation

Most shape parametrisation methods require manual setup. Setting up auxiliary grids for lattice-based methods, such as e.g. auxiliary grids with Hicks-Henne bumps on aerofoils or stacked spline curves for turbomachinery blades, involve substantial effort and are difficult to extend to complex geometries. Free-form deformations such as volume splines require the definition of auxiliary hexahedral volume grids that need to be snapped to the geometry to preserve features.

In the node-based parametrisation, displacements of the surface grid nodes are the design variables which offers the richest design space the CFD

discretisation can consider. As a matter of fact, this design space is even too rich for the CFD as the parametrisation method can express high-frequency modes which are not adequately resolved by the CFD and hence remain poorly damped. Additional regularisation is necessary, and implicit [3] as well as explicit smoothing methods have been proposed, both of them requiring tune a smoothing coefficient. The disadvantage of the method is that the optimal shape exists only as a mesh, transcription to CAD is not straightforward and any approximation will incur a loss of optimality. A widely used CAD-based approach is to employ parametrisation directly on the parametric CAD model and requires the derivatives of surface points with respect to the design parameters. Typically, the shape derivatives are not available within the closed source commercial CAD systems. In this work, the differentiated open-source CAD kernel OpenCascade Technology(OCCT) is used to provide shape derivatives and modify the geometry in the optimisation design loop.

As an alternative, the CAD based approach NSPCC as proposed by Xu et al. [4] uses the control points of the NURBS surface patches as design variables. Hence it represents the richest design space that CAD can express. The CAD description is kept inside the optimisation loop and produces the optimal shape in STEP format. To enforce continuity between patches such as G1 (tangency) or G2 (curvature), constraint equations are numerically evaluated at test points distributed along the patch interfaces. The Jacobian of the constraint equations is assembled and the design space is the kernel of this Jacobian which is evaluated using a Singular Value Decomposition. The design variables then effectively become the vectors associated with non-singular values.

2: Test case

In this paper performance, efficiency and capabilities of the both CAD and node-based methods are discussed and compared on an internal turbine cooling channel U-Bend test case. The geometry of the U-Bend is consisting of three parts inlet, outlet and walls. An inlet velocity of $v=8.8m/s$, with density of $1.203kg/m^3$ and no-slip walls are used as boundary conditions. These boundary conditions results in a turbulent flow with Reynolds number of 40,000 based on the hydraulic diameter of the pipe at the inlet, $D_h = 0.075m$. The goal of the optimisation process is to deform the 180 degree joints connecting the adjacent channel passages to minimise the mass averaged total pressure loss.

3: Results and Discussion

Adjoint based aerodynamic shape optimisation of an internal turbine cooling channel using both CAD and node-based parametrisation method is performed. In each design step, the adjoint method allows for the computation of whole surface sensitivities with only two solver calls, a primal and an adjoint solver call. These surface sensitivities are coupled with the steepest descent optimisation algorithm with Armijo-Wolfe based line search condition to deform the U-Bend in the direction of improvement. Fig. 1 shows the mid plane velocity field of the initial U-Bend. There is a large area of separated flow near the 180 degree turn part of the U-Bend which will add to the total pressure loss. The aerodynamic optimisation of the U-Bend aims at reducing the region of flow separation to obtain minimum pressure loss between the outlet and the inlet.

Figure 1: Velocity Field at the mid plane of the Initial Geometry.

Fig. 2 shows the comparison of velocity magnitude of optimised geometries obtained after 16% pressure drop using both node and CAD-based parametrisation method with respect to the original circular U-bend. Velocity magnitude of the optimised geometry show that the area of the flow separation is significantly reduced and exhibits much weaker secondary flows. These preliminary results are obtained using coarse mesh. In the presentation optimisation results will be discussed by comparing the final pressure drop, flow fields and shape variations between the both parametrisation methods using fine mesh.

Figure 2: Comparison of velocity magnitude of optimised geometry: Node-based (left) and CAD-based (right)

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